

Revealing Emotional Space Using Representational Techniques of Installation Artists in Architectural Design Education

Jeffrey Haase, The Ohio State University, Department of Industrial, Interior and Visual Communication Design – USA

Abstract

Architects and Interior Designers have an insurmountable problem within the process of design. Our language consists of two-dimensional explanations about three-dimensional events. Drawings, consisting mostly of plans, elevations and perspectives make up the majority of these archaic methods. In addition, our ability to educate is handicapped by the dynamic difference in scale that exists between these tools and the environments they represent. We often explore designs at 1/50th to 1/100th their actual size. Our ideas are about being inside looking out, but our representation and education techniques are always placing us outside looking in.

This paper will examine alternative methods of spatial representation that address scale, dimension and more importantly the perceptual and emotional components of our designed environments. The resulting projects utilized representational methods often attributed to Installation Artists. These interior spaces designed for gallery settings presented an architectural dialog while existing within the framework of installation art, revealing an emotional component often attributed to art, but usually hidden in our understanding of architectural space and the interior environments we inhabit everyday.

Keywords: Emotional Representation, Interior Design

Introduction

Architects and Interior Designers have an insurmountable problem within the process of design. Our language consists of two-dimensional explanations about three-dimensional events. Drawings, consisting mostly of plans, elevations and perspectives make up the majority of these archaic methods. In addition, our ability to educate is handicapped by the dynamic difference in scale that exists between these tools and the environments they represent. We often explore designs at 1/50th to 1/100th their actual size. Our ideas are about being inside looking out, but our representation and education techniques are always placing us outside looking in.

Designers need alternative methods of spatial representation that address scale, dimension, and more importantly, the perceptual and emotional components of our designed environments. The following is a series of notes that outline and describe alternative methods

of working. These methods not only address the historical pitfalls of architectural representational methods, but also reveal the emotional component often attributed to art, but usually missing in our understanding of architectural spaces and the interior environments we inhabit every day.

Problem of communication

Humans have always grappled with the problem of representation as a means of communication. Lawyers fight with language and the written word; Cartographers are continually challenged by the vast dimensional qualities of our planet. Microbiologists and chemists try to overcome the infinitely small and always changing universe with symbols and diagrams that try to convey both physical and chemical process relationships. Most of these professions, like design, use only one, two, or maybe three methods of traditionally accepted representational techniques to communicate their respective ideas. Because of this, practitioners must rely on end users to have some previous knowledge about these used conventions. But do we? How many of us can actually understand a lawyers brief, realize what really exists topologically between here and the next point on a map, or look at the molecule diagram for coffee and understand how the carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen are creating the bitter taste and enhancing our ability to stay awake? As designers, we often leave our clients and end users (even some of our colleagues) in the dark about our ideas. Too often, after months of presenting floor plans, elevations, and sections our constructed designs still surprise our clients, and in many cases, the transformation from paper to reality surprises us as well.

As an educator, I'm always searching for alternative methods of communication that provide insight to the complexity of spatial design. Traditional methods are disappointing in their inability to communicate intelligently about our large scale multidimensional designs. Students often graduate from a design program with the belief that the ideas they convey on paper and present in traditional formats are "real." This misperception is dangerous and leads to an ever widening gap between what we design and what we build. In addition, practitioners who are forever suffocated by the technicalities of an architectural project seem to forget the emotional qualities that exist within our built environment.

The Alternative

I would like to propose an alternative educational method of working that provides missing insight into the emotional, dimensional, social, and realistic conditions that professional designers face. This proposed representational way of working was originally set out to unlock truths about place, and to bridge the gap that exists between doing Architecture (professionals) and thinking about Architecture (academic studios). In the following case studies, participating students were exposed to many hands-on experiences rarely found in traditional studio courses. They explored: creative construction methods, three dimensional problem solving techniques, budget management, and team building skills. Furthermore, due to the gallery component of these projects the emotional responses to a space were reflected upon, studied and influenced design decisions and directions.

Emotion and the gallery affect

Out of the other professions I have researched, one group, known as “Installation” or “Environment” artists, overcome the constraints of a limited source of representation methods. They rely on an endless supply of representational techniques, and they include the end user in the representational model often as part of the representation itself. Their work reflects on and often encourages the emotional and political conditions between the user/observer and the designed space. The scale of their ideas often equals the scale of the results. Artists like Gordon Matta-Clark manipulated existing spaces and used his raw form of photography to capture the emotional essence of his scarred and carved interiors. Vito Acconci used common and non common interior elements as large scale sculptural effects in “Flying Floors” 1995-8, and “Tilted Exhibition” 1993. Goro Hirata’s wax room, “Mind Space,” in Pittsburgh’s Mattress Factory gallery glowed in a way no interior glazing could ever do. Do-Ho Suh in “Perfect Room” demonstrated the beauty of interior surface by reconstructing a full scale interior using translucent cloth. These artists constantly bridge the realm between architect/designer and artist. Their installations and manipulations of existing spaces are always emotionally charged and are constructed at full scale. They encourage debate and conversation about emotional issues of a place, including how different materials, lighting effects, and sequential movement through an environment can elicit different emotional responses from its inhabitants.

Their work often begins at one place (artist studio or specific site) and is transported or re-represented in a traditional or non-traditional art gallery. This is an important component of the work for it needs to convey itself as both original and representation. This dichotomy often blurs the gap between “represented ideas” and “real,” something we rarely experience as designers. In the context of an art gallery, work is almost always measured with an emotional scale. Function, though it may be present is not considered. Debate and discussion about the installation is encouraged and often necessary for the work to exist. Commercial interior spaces, on the other hand, are rarely measured (in their built stage) with an emotional thermometer and often are merely considered functional results about functional ideas. In depth discussions and debate about these designed spaces are rarely tackled. It is precisely this “in-between” realm of art and architecture that provided the inspiration for the methods and work described below.

Case Studies

Wasserstrom Warehouse #3

I was first introduced to this alternative method of working in the spring of 1990, at The Ohio State University. We were interested in exploring issues of architecture outside of the political confines of the University “studio” context. We (Professor Frank Fantauzzi, one fine arts MFA, three graduate and three undergraduate architecture students) acquired a warehouse space for one quarter (ten weeks) to be used as an architectural laboratory. In addition, we were provided with a small gallery/studio space back at the University. This was a place to display continued updates of our off-campus activities. Participants, through the inspirational icons of Gordon Matta-Clark and Vito Acconci were encouraged to use architectural processes to express ideas about the reality of our profession, which included: gravity, materiality, representation vs. real, measurement, scale, and the definition of work. Our first contact with the “real” space felt more like archeology than architecture. We scraped, drilled, cut and thoroughly explored the existing conditions of the six story warehouse. We constructed a makeshift darkroom and used “on the spot” black and white photography as our recording tool of choice. We quickly realized the kind of effort it takes to singularly affect an environment. Drawing a wall might take half a minute while building one by yourself might take a day and a half depending on the method of construction. Our project ideas began to focus on small events within the space. We made horizontal elevators (a seat

that swings over a two story space to a remote room) and hydraulic teeter-totters (a 15 foot hydraulic piston attached to a giant wood beam that lowered an individual to the floor below). These systems replaced traditional “comfortable” methods of transportation with moments of fear as you sat in a small chair hovering over the floor below or stood cautiously on the end of a beam while it slowly lowered you to safety. Other projects included:

Collapsed room: This project dismantled an existing overhead machine room and reconstructed a proportionally scaled solid model from its walls. The existing 3-dimensional space was replaced with a two dimensional representation (full size black and white photograph).

1/4 inch = 2,753 pounds: The issue of “Architectural scale” was the focus of this project. An Architects traditional understanding of scale is blindly understood as 1/4 inch = 1 foot-0 inches (the scale often used for drawing and model building). This scale within the context of a real space seems quite meaningless. As a counterpoint to this skewed view of reality, a steel floor beam was deflected 1/4 of an inch in order to pinch/support a column. To achieve this 1/4 inch deflection required using 2,753 pounds of window weights that had been removed from the building’s existing bricked-in windows.

Jobsite- An Acoustical Rendering of a Construction site: This project consisted of a large wood box built from existing shipping crates filled with power tools. Photographs of the tools inside the box were formatted in a way that mimicked floor plans (overhead view) and elevations (front and side profile views). The box was placed in the center of an “exhibit/studio space” and was rigged so that tools inside would turn on for 60 seconds every hour. This was the advent of sound as a representational measure of constructed Architecture.

Trash pile: This project measured the architectural work that was produced by all of the students on each floor of the warehouse. All of the construction debris left behind was pushed into a twenty foot circle in the center of each floor and visually recorded.

Figure 1, Collapsed room:

Figure 2, $\frac{1}{4}$ inch = 2753pounds

Figure 3, Jobsite

Figure 4, Trash Pile

In my eight years of professional experience prior to this studio, I was amazed that, despite the abstract results, the process of working this way was more like “real” architecture than anything I had remembered in undergraduate school. Our responsibilities and decisions were based on real space issues such as gravity, detailing, materiality, structural elements, budget, scale, and marketing (for our weekly and end of the quarter exhibit). In addition, our decision making process always included emotional content. We discussed and speculated about the reactions others would have when confronting our resulting projects.

Process images of the work along with actual objects were displayed within a studio space designated for the class at the university. This studio/gallery space was changed weekly, and it was here, that we learned about the emotional components of a gallery setting. Our work was often assaulted verbally and even physically. The project “Jobsite” (see figure 3) was damaged in an attempt to shut it off, and the photographs were ripped and written on denouncing the work as valid architecture. Students and faculty alike debated the works contribution to Architecture. They felt it belonged in the school of Art. Some went as far as to question the purpose of the studio and threatened to cancel it mid quarter. This emotional debate unearthed varying views about the definition of architectural work, style in architecture vs. style in art, and our general activities off campus in Wasserstrom Warehouse #3. Our continued efforts to show our work as “real” due to its scale and materiality versus

the paper “unreal” world of the traditional studio often fueled the fire. The debate always erupted around the aesthetic of the “result,” rarely the validity of the process. This occurred because our “results” did not resemble traditional architectural representation and was therefore invalid as architecture to many. Our (the studio’s) philosophy was that “Architecture” is only a process and “Construction” is the result of that process. We intended to transform Architecture into a verb (constructing a thought) rather than its perceived noun based tradition (the thought as a construction). The political differences of making spaces vs. the academic approach of thinking about spaces fueled the emotional controversy. There was no structured forum to control this debate. The discussions were heated and ran rampant through the school, both as positive and negative emotions.

In Art, the emotion of a topic or a place is often the core of the exploration that leads to the result. In architecture/interior design we might start with an emotional desire, often expressed in an abstract way, such as the client desiring the atmosphere of the space to evoke a certain emotion, or the desire for a sequence of spaces to provoke an idea about a theme, brand or corporate process. As a design’s complexity, regulations, functions, and cost consume the process of the project, the emotional component (if it ever existed) is often eradicated. The art or exhibit/gallery component of these “alternative” projects makes it impossible to separate emotion from the result.

The Oval

At The Ohio State University the main outdoor “lawn” is known as “The Oval.” It has been referred to as the center of campus and often becomes the outdoor playground, the place for demonstrations, the sun-tanning booth and the main social center for students and faculty alike. In a recent project entitled “The Oval: A Perceptual Sensorium” (figure 5), the Oval was re-represented in a gallery space near its edge. Methods of representing its dimensions, its experiential components and its cognitive place within the built campus were some of the projects explorative goals. The methods of representing these issues resulted in pouring large 3 inch thick wax molds at the Oval’s North, East, South, and West boundaries. Imbedded in these wax blocks was string that stretched across the lawn to the adjacent block. Over several weeks the trash, leaves and debris were raked up from the multi-acre plot. This acquired material was stored and used to produce 800 black and white photograms (process of developing a black and white photograph by placing actual material onto the contact paper and exposing it to light) The photograms were carefully pinned on to panels using

entomology pins to emulate the layering quality of the original debris. Finally, video tape was made of the string by walking along its length, providing a noise component to the experience. The Gallery was filled along its edge with the collected debris. The walls were wrapped with the photogrammed imagery of the material that is commonly under one's feet. The string (roughly a mile's worth) that identified the dimension of width and length, was suspended from the wax blocks at the polar coordinates of the room, with the excess pooled in the middle of the gallery, underneath hanging televisions that displayed a video of the pacing across The Oval. Visitors were surrounded by the imagery, sounds, smells and represented dimensions of The Oval as they traveled around the gallery. A "gallery talk", describing the process, provided the audience an open forum to receive feedback about the gallery experience. Many visitors revealed an emotional connection to the represented Oval, with the sounds and smells as the clearest identifier. A designer would rarely think about using sound and smell as a representational tool yet it was this sensory stimulus that provoked a memory of the space being represented.

Figure 5, The Oval: A Perceptual Sensorium

What's your color?

Another project included ten undergraduate students who were eager to work in a non-traditional way. They were given the opportunity to develop and construct a gallery exhibit that expressed an aspect of interior design. The students and instructor decided to look at the

Color Marketing Group (CMG) and their claim to predict future color trends in society. We felt there was a “prediction component” that felt a lot like persuasive suggestion due to the CMG’s popularity and influence in the market place. By researching and debating this topic, we created an emotional and controversial base for design ideas. The final exhibit consisted of painted fabric ceiling and wall panels that could be quickly turned around in order to change the galleries color half way through the two week exhibit. Projection screens were illuminated with color geometric images each coming from two separate slide projectors. As a viewer went through the exhibit to read the panels about the Color Marketing Group and view the color vignettes, they would create shadows that disrupted half of the projected images (figure 6-7). Regardless of the theme or the exhibit’s result, it was the process that provided the most educational reward for both the students and the instructor. During the designing, planning, and construction of this “exhibit,” we explored the emotional connections between color and space and tried to design a communication device (representational result) that addressed those ideas. It was amazing how the students were thinking and solving problems differently than they had in the typical studio, and how those new creative problem-solving techniques were so inherently similar to professional ones. Some of the many issues we encountered were:

- Emotion:

In traditional studios emotional issues about spatial design can only be assumed. It is not until a designer has been through the entire process of a project (idea to completed construction) that they can begin to understand the emotional impact a designer has on the spaces they design.

- Collaborative design:

From the beginning, the decisions were assumed to be made and agreed upon by the entire team. A team-oriented project simulates a typical design firm’s approach to problem solving.

- Material use and cost:

The students relied on the instructor for some of the material options available, but they were encouraged to be creative and resourceful when it came to acquiring both money and materials.

- Budgeting:

There never seems to be enough money for actual materials. In this case, estimating was not just an exercise on paper, but was actually verified when the project was completed. In

addition, many ideas were redesigned in order to reduce scrap and overages of precious materials.

- Construction methods:

As an instructor, it is difficult to talk about construction sequencing when detailing, or explaining how materials can be shaped or manipulated. The first time a student tries to build full scale what they have drawn-- the result often fails. Tools and technique knowledge were important, and the students often learned the hard way about sequencing and construction techniques.

- Gravity:

Gravity is often one of the most misunderstood and overlooked conditions of design. Students develop the belief that a paper and foam core model represents the proportions and connections needed to understand reality.

- Details:

Detailing is a profession within our profession. Students rarely leave undergraduate programs with creative knowledge about material connections, proportions, mechanisms, flexibility etc. These alternative method projects are the only way I have found to introduce creative detailing techniques by hands-on instruction.

- Scale:

This is clearly the most important lesson: what happens to ideas when they get big. All real projects are designed and re-designed at many different scales. The awareness of that fact encourages better design decisions at the beginning of a project.

Figure 6 and 7, View of the exhibit “What’s your Color?”
During the first week of the exhibit /During the second week of the exhibit

Findings

Students in some of the projects described above and others similar to them were asked to leave traditional educational techniques behind in order to explore alternative ways of expression and communication about built environments. They were asked to work in groups and apply creative problem solving skills to real problems. They expressed gained knowledge of emotional and political conditions within interior spaces. They began to understand the complexities of designing three dimensional spaces at full scale and working within “real” budgets, in lieu of traditional “paper” exercises. Furthermore, the results addressed the larger issues of emotional place, and it’s relation to function and space planning. After this experience many of the students experimented with mock-ups and non-traditional methods of communication when immersed back into a traditional studio environment. Their contributions enhanced the traditional studio experience for others as well as for themselves. These alternative studios were testimony to the potential of this method’s ability to provide an understanding of the link between emotion and place, in addition to providing hands-on professional design experience.

Conclusions

Non-traditional methods are not expected to replace traditional methods of representation, which are far too infused and valuable to the profession. Instead, adding these methods allow students to explore the emotional conditions within a space (effects of different materials, spatial confinement, color response, etc.), without the restraints often present in traditional interior architecture (regulations, functional complexities, historic precedent, etc). This is a result of the “gallery affect”. In addition, this method provides young designers the opportunity to solve “real” design issues that often exist outside the typical academic studio. The challenge is for other programs to integrate similar activities to their design curriculum to produce students that think laterally, have working knowledge of professional design challenges, and that understand the emotional content within interior environments. “If the only tool you have is a hammer, you tend to see every problem as a nail.” (Abraham Maslow).

REFERENCES

Acconci, Vito. 1993. "Interior images of Tilted Exhibition and Flying Floors." tilted exhibition 1998 Flying floors. [Online] Vito Acconci's studio website. Available from URL: <<http://www.acconci.com>> [Accessed 2003 August 28th]

Crow, T. and Diserens, C. 2003. *Gordon Matta-Clark*. Phaidon Press.

Hirata, Goro. 1999. "Mind Space." [Online] The Mattress Factory. Available from URL: <<http://www.mattress.org/catalogue/99/index.html#>> [Accessed 2003 September 10th]

Kwinter, S. and Sobel, D. 2001. *Vito Acconci: Acts of Architecture*. Milwaukee Art Museum.

Suh, Do Ho. 2003. "Perfect Home." [Online] The David Winton Bell Gallery List site at Brown University. Available from URL: <http://www.brown.edu/Facilities/David_Winton_Bell_Gallery/suh.html#seoulhome>. [Accessed 2003 August 24th]

Reiss, J. 2000. *From Margin to Center: The Spaces of Installation Art*. MIT Press

Prof. Jeffrey Haase is an Assistant Professor at the Ohio State University in the department of Industrial, Interior and Visual Communication Design. He graduated from University of Kentucky's College of Architecture in 1984, received his masters in Architecture in 1991 at The Ohio State University. While a Principal at Design Collective Incorporated he was involved as design lead for many published commercial projects. His current academic research at The Ohio State University is concerned with the role and importance of idea and place representation within the disciplines of Interior Design and Architecture. He is specifically exploring alternative ways of representing ideas and environment designs to better understand issues of scale, spatial perception, emotional content, location mapping, and communication of successful vs. non-successful designs.